

Order of elemental analysis

*You can bring your samples (min 5 mg) to Sylvie (lab 07) on Mondays and Thursdays **between 9:30am and 11:00am***

Customer

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Sample

Sample name: ARN038 [Cu(Xantphos)(1,1'-biisoquinoline)][PF ₆]	
Aspect / texture: Powder	
Molecular formula: C ₅₇ H ₄₄ CuF ₆ N ₂ OP ₃	Molar mass: 1043.45
Used solvent: Dichloromethane, Diethylether	
Structure:	

Sample details

Is the sample harmful? (skin, lungs, toxic)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample light sensitive?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample electrostatic?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample hygroscopic?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Do you want your sample back?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Additional informations:		

Elemental analysis

Sample name: ARN038

Single determination

Double determination

C <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	N <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other elements: Cu, P, O, F		

Results

Analysis number: 2020-53			
Sample name: ARN038			
Expected values:	C 65.61 %	H 4.25 %	N 2.68 %
Results:	C 65.58 % - %	H 4.73 % - %	N 2.40 % - %
Other elements:			
Remarks: When F → single determination → HF			

Date/Visa operator
 29.07.2020, Sylvie Mittelheisser